

Removal of Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺ from Aqueous Media with Linden Tree (*Tilia vulgaris*) Leaves: Environmentally Friendly Adsorption and Optimization

Duygu ŞİRİN, Türkan BÖRKLÜ BUDAK*

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Art and Science, Yıldız Technical University,
34220 İstanbul, Türkiye

Abstract

Efforts have been made to develop a natural, inexpensive, and readily available adsorbent material for removing Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺ heavy metals from water. In this study, the removal of Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺ from water was tested using Linden tree (*Tilia vulgaris*) leaves. After collection, the leaves were rinsed, and moisture was removed by heating at 80 °C for 24 hours. The prepared adsorbent for experiments was then sieved through a 60-80 mesh sieve. Linden leaves were separately added to solutions containing Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺, and the percentage removal was measured. The results showed that Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺ ions could be effectively removed using Linden leaves. In this study, the adsorption capacity was analyzed by varying initial concentrations, amount of adsorbent, contact time, temperature, and shaking speed.

The results show that linden leaves effectively removed Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺ cations with efficiencies of 85.83% and 95.94%, respectively. The adsorption characteristics indicate that linden leaves can interact with Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺ cations, making them suitable for environmental applications. Additionally, the data suggest that linden leaves could provide a new, cost-effective, and eco-friendly method for reducing environmental pollution and enhancing water quality. This research is expected to contribute significantly to practical solutions for environmental issues by using natural plants.

Keywords: Adsorption, *Tilia Vulgaris*, Linden, Fe³⁺, Fe²⁺

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the main causes of water pollution, in terms of both quantity and quality, is population growth and the accidental release of industrial waste into the environment [1]. The substances considered to be wastewater include heavy metals, inorganic and organic pollutants, and microbiological wastes, which are categorized as industrial waste, as well as domestic waste from humans [2].

Heavy metals from industries such as electrolysis, fossil fuel extraction, electroplating, and mining are significant non-biodegradable pollutants. These include iron (Fe), lead (Pb), chromium (Cr), copper (Cu), arsenic (As), zinc (Zn), cesium (Cs), mercury (Hg), and cadmium (Cd) [3]. The erosion of the Earth's crust and increased erosion caused by the buildup of these toxic compounds are global concerns [4].

Iron, a heavy metal, is the fourth most common element in the Earth's crust and plays a vital role in the growth and maintenance of almost all living organisms [5]. For example, besides forming the building blocks of essential biological molecules such as hemoglobin, myoglobin, catalase, and cytochromes, the ability to switch between Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} cations is a crucial process that supports various biological redox reactions [6]. However, exposure to high doses can lead to toxic effects. Therefore, addressing water pollution caused by heavy metal ions, reducing toxicity, and promoting recycling are becoming increasingly important.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials and Reagents

A solution containing Fe^{2+} cations was prepared using $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (molecular weight: 392.15 g/mol, Merck), while a solution with Fe^{3+} cations was made from $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (molecular weight: 270.33 g/mol, Merck). A 0.1 M KSCN solution, needed for forming the complex, was prepared in 1 liter; its molecular weight is 97.18 g/mol. Additionally, 10% (w/w) 1,10-phenanthroline and a 0.1 M HCl solution were supplied by Merck.

Two different methods were used to measure the amounts of Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} over time. For Fe^{3+} , 0.5 mL of 0.1 M KSCN and 0.5 mL of 0.1 M HCl solution were added to 5 mL of the working solution. The resulting colored complex was measured with a UV spectrophotometer at 470 nm. Similarly, 30 μL of 10% 1-10 phenanthroline was added to 5 mL of the Fe^{2+} containing solution, and this colored solution was measured at 510 nm on the same device. Changes in iron concentrations after adsorption were tracked using calibration curves created with standard solutions.

Figure 1 *Tilia vulgaris* (linden) leaves [7,8].

In the study, linden (*Tilia*) leaves, shown in Figure 1, were used as the adsorbent material. The leaves collected from Istanbul, Turkey, were first washed, dried in an oven at 80 °C, ground, and then passed through a 60-80 mesh sieve.

A Julabo SW 22 model shaking water bath was used during the studies conducted with the batch adsorption method. Solution samples taken during the adsorption process were processed as needed and then measured with an Agilent 8453 UV-VIS spectrophotometer. All working solutions were prepared using distilled water from a Mikrotest MSD-08 purification device. All sedimentation steps were performed with an Electromag M615 model centrifuge.

2.2. Adsorption Studies

Adsorption experiments were conducted using the batch method. The adsorbent material used to remove Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} cations from aqueous solution was obtained from the leaves of *Tilia Vulgaris*. Working solutions were prepared by diluting appropriate amounts of a 1000 mg/L stock solution. The effects of various parameters, including initial iron concentration (5-50 mg/L), adsorbent amount (0.1-1.5 g), adsorption time (5-180 min), and ambient temperature (25-40 °C), on adsorption efficiency were investigated. A specific amount of adsorbent was weighed into a 100

mL beaker. A solution with a certain cation concentration was added and kept in a water bath at a set temperature and agitation speed. After the adsorption period, the solution was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 3 minutes and filtered through filter paper. The colored complex formed by adding reagents to 5 mL of the filtrate was measured on a UV spectrophotometer at $\lambda_{\max} = 470$ nm for Fe^{3+} and $\lambda_{\max} = 510$ nm for Fe^{2+} . Using Equations 1 and 2, the % removal and Q_e adsorption capacity were calculated.

$$\%R = \frac{C_0 - C_e}{C_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$Q_e = \frac{C_0 - C_e}{m} \times V \quad (2)$$

In the equations above, C_0 (mg/L) represents the initial concentration of the specific cation, C_e (mg/L) denotes the concentration of the cation at any given time, %R indicates the removal percentage, Q_e (mg/g) shows the adsorption capacity, m (g) is the amount of adsorbent, and V (L) indicates the volume of solution.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. The effect of the beginning concentration of Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} on adsorption

To study the effect of initial concentration, a key factor affecting adsorption efficiency, solutions with Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} were tested separately at levels from 5 to 50 mg/L. Other parameters such as the amount of adsorbent, solution volume, agitation speed, temperature, and duration were kept constant at 1.5 g, 50 mL, 150 rpm, 25 °C, and 60 minutes.

Figure 2. Investigation of the effect of the beginning concentration of Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} on the % removal value.

Figure 3. Investigation of how the initial amounts of Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} affect removal efficiency.

As shown in Figures 2 and 3, the optimal beginning concentration for Fe^{3+} was 99.88% removal at 30 mg/L, and for Fe^{2+} , it was 78.99% removal at 5 mg/L

3.2. The impact of adsorbent amount on Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺ removal

To examine the effect of linden tree leaves on Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺, a total of 12 glass beakers were weighed separately, and specific amounts (0.1-1.5 g) of adsorbent were added. 50 mL of 30 mg/L Fe³⁺ and 30 mg/L Fe²⁺ were then added to the flasks. The solutions were shaken at a constant speed of 150 rpm for 60 minutes at 25°C. The same procedure was used to calculate the % removal values. The results are shown in Figures 4 and 5.

Figure 4. Investigation of the effect of different adsorbent amounts on Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺ % removal values.

Figure 5. Investigation of the effect of different adsorbent amounts on Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺ adsorption capacities.

Based on the data, the optimal amount of adsorbent for Fe^{3+} cation was found to be 1.5 g, while for Fe^{2+} it was 0.9 g.

3.3. The temporal effect of iron removal

The contact time at the optimal value is the shortest duration needed for the linden tree leaf adsorbent to reach saturation during the peak efficiency of Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} metals (adsorbates), as indicated by the high removal percentage (%R).

To examine the effect of contact time, we prepared solutions by adding 1.5 g of 30 mg/L Fe^{3+} and 0.9 g of 5 mg/L Fe^{2+} individually to 100 mL glass beakers. The solutions were shaken at 150 rpm at room temperature (25°C) for a duration of 5 to 180 minutes. Afterward, the same procedure was used to calculate the percentage removal values. The results for the optimal percentage removal efficiency of Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} metals are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Investigation of how contact time affects the removal percentages of Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} .

As shown in Figure 6, the linden tree leaf adsorbent achieved the highest removal efficiency of Fe^{3+} in 60 minutes, while Fe^{2+} reached its peak removal efficiency in 15 minutes.

3.4. Temperature effect

To assess the effect of ambient temperature on adsorption, 50 mL of each metal solution was tested at the optimal concentrations (30 mg/L for Fe^{3+} and 5 mg/L for Fe^{2+}), shaken at 150 rpm for the

ideal contact times (60 minutes for Fe^{3+} and 15 minutes for Fe^{2+}) across temperatures ranging from 25°C to 50°C . After each contact period at each temperature, the same procedure was repeated.

The best removal efficiency values are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Examining the impact of temperature on Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} removal percentages.

It shows that the highest percentage removal (%R) of Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} metals was observed at temperatures of 40°C and 50°C , respectively.

3.5. Agitation rate effect

To evaluate how shaking speed affects adsorption efficiency, experiments were performed with these parameters: 50 mL, 30 mg/L Fe^{3+} , 1.5 g adsorbent, 40°C , and 60 minutes; for Fe^{2+} , 50 mL, 5 mg/L, 0.9 g adsorbent, 50°C , and 15 minutes. Shaking speeds ranged from 100 to 200 rpm. The results are presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Examining the impact of agitation rate on Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺ removal percentages.

Examining the data in Figure 8 shows that a shaking speed of 180 rpm is the optimal value for both cations.

3.6. Regeneration studies

To evaluate the reusability of lime tree leaves as an adsorbent, a regeneration process was performed. For this purpose, 0.1 M HCl and 0.1 M NaOH solutions were used. After adsorption under optimal conditions, the adsorbent treated with the regeneration solutions was thoroughly rinsed three times with distilled water and then dried at 55 °C for 24 hours in an oven. The regenerated lime leaf adsorbent was subsequently reused in the Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺ adsorption tests. The results are shown in Figures 9.

Figure 9. Evaluation of the regeneration effect on the adsorbent material.

As shown in Figure 9, the adsorbent material effectively removes relevant cations even after regeneration.

Conclusion

This study investigated the adsorption capacity of linden tree leaves as an adsorbent for removing heavy metals, specifically iron(III) and iron(II). Under optimal conditions, removal efficiencies reached 85.83% for Fe(III) and 95.94% for Fe(II). The optimal parameters for the experiments included 1.5 g of adsorbent for Fe(III), a 50 ml solution volume, a 30 mg/L solution concentration, an ambient temperature of 40 °C, a contact time of 60 minutes, and a shaking speed of 180 rpm. For Fe(II), the parameters were 0.9 g of adsorbent, 50 ml solution volume, 5 mg/L solution concentration, 50°C temperature, 15 minutes contact time, and 180 rpm stirring speed. Additionally, regeneration tests assessed whether linden leaves could be reused after a single adsorption cycle, using 0.1 M NaOH and 0.1 M HCl. These regeneration experiments with these solutions achieved high percentage removal values. The results show that linden tree leaves are highly effective in removing Fe(III) and Fe(II), providing valuable insights for future research. This method is simple, cost-effective, and efficient for wastewater treatment, offering an environmentally friendly approach that eliminates the need for additional chemicals.

References

- [1] Razzak, S. A., Faruque, M. O., Alsheikh, Z., Alsheikhmohamad, L., Alkuroud, D., Alfayez, A., Hossain, S. M. Z., & Hossain, M. M. (2022). *A comprehensive review on conventional and biological-driven heavy metals removal from industrial wastewater*. *Environmental Advances*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envadv.2022.100168>
- [2] Bibi, M., Rashid, J., Iqbal, A., & Xu, M. (2023). *Multivariate analysis of heavy metals in pharmaceutical wastewaters of National Industrial Zone, Rawat, Pakistan*. *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth*, 130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pce.2023.103398>
- [3] Montagnaro, F., & Santoro, L. (2009). *Reuse of coal combustion ashes as dyes and heavy metal adsorbents: Effect of sieving and demineralization on waste properties and adsorption capacity*. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 150(1), 174–180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2008.12.02>
- [4] Fei, Y., & Hu, Y. H. (2023). *Recent progress in removal of heavy metals from wastewater: A comprehensive review*. In *Chemosphere* (Vol. 335). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2023.139077>
- [5] Ngah, W. S. W., Ab Ghani, S., & Kamari, A. (2005). *Adsorption behaviour of Fe(II) and Fe(III) ions in aqueous solution on chitosan and cross-linked chitosan beads*. *Bioresource Technology*, 96(4), 443–450. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2004.05.022>
- [6] Phippen, B. C., Horvath, C., Nordin, R., & Nagpal, N. (2008). *Ambient aquatic life guidelines for iron: overview report*. *Water Stewardship Division, Ministry of Environment*.
- [7] https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Tilia_vulgaris._Tilleira.jpg
- [8] <https://www.first-nature.com/trees/tilia-vulgaris.php>